

Interview questions and protocol

Preamble Script

<Introductions>

Hello, thank you for agreeing to take time to participate in our research study. The purpose of this research is to understand the role technology plays in how small and micro-businesses run by members of groups at risk of harm are attacked online. We are interested in knowing the different types of harms facilitated by technology that businesses like the one you **run/own** may face, how **<platforms>** might help or hinder these attacks, and hear your suggestions for how things could be different to improve digital safety for all.

Were you able to read in full the information sheet and consent form that I shared with you? Did you have anything that you wanted to ask about before we get started? I am happy to use this time to answer them!

<pause for potential questions>

Okay so this will take about 60 minutes in total, starting with 5 minutes at the start to explain and walk through the consent form in front of you, which goes over what the study will discuss, reiterates that participation is voluntary, and asks for consent to record this interview for our notetaking purposes. We will then move into the interview, where we will ask you about ~10 questions regarding your experiences as a small business owner that uses technology and online services for their business. We will also cover your experiences with the business itself, experiences of economic abuse with this business, and paths to recovery you have explored/would like to see. This portion should take no longer than about 50 minutes. Then, we will move into the last 5 minutes, where we will inform you of any next steps following this study, does this sound good to you?

In this study, we will ask and discuss experiences associated with potentially being the target of digital attacks which you might find distressing; the risk to you is no greater than the risk of discussing this with a trusted friend or a trained professional. However, if you feel uncomfortable continuing please feel free to stop me, take a break, or quit at any time and you will not suffer any penalty for doing so.

Okay so, let's get started ...

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New Script.

<small talk, introductions>

Thank you for taking the time to participate in our study! In this work, we're exploring how technology impacts small and micro-businesses run by individuals at greater risk of harm, particularly in facing online attacks. We want to understand the types of harm businesses like yours face, how <platform-of-use> may help or hinder these attacks, and your suggestions for improving digital safety for all.

Were you able to review the information sheet and consent form? Do you have any questions before we begin?

<pause for potential questions>

This session will take about 60 minutes. We'll be asking ~10 questions about your experiences as a small business owner using technology and online services. We'll also discuss your business, any experiences of challenging financial situations caused by these technologies, and recovery paths you've explored or would like to see—this should take about 50 minutes. Finally, we'll spend 5 minutes going over the next steps. We'll discuss your experiences with digital attacks, which may be distressing to you. The risk is no greater than discussing it with a trusted friend or professional. If at any point you feel uncomfortable, you're free to pause, take a break, or stop.

*Do we have your permission to take notes in this session?
And audio record the session?*

General starter questions

Purpose: to get a sense of the business type, and how this interfaces with technology

To start, I'd like to know a little bit more about your business ...

- Could you tell me a short history about your business, including your motivation behind starting the business, what you sell, how long you've been running/managing the business?
- So you mentioned that you use <online marketplace(s)> to conduct /advertise your business, how did you decide on using these marketplaces?
Prompt: benefits or restrictions of specific marketplaces, cost, 'just happened'
- Okay, and do you use other online or digital platforms for promoting your business, or managing payments? Can you walk me through how that works?
Prompt: customized paid ads, square/cashApp

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- Are there any other uses of digital technologies in your business that you think we haven't covered?

Prompt: recruitment, reporting, online listings, search engine optimization

Customer-interactions

Purpose: Understanding the (potential) starting points of attacks

- How would you summarize your online customer base?
Prompt: any demographics, online/offline, one-time purchasers vs subscribers
- How do customers come to find out about your business? Can they contact you about services/products through this method?
Prompt: suggest common communication channels (e.g., direct messages, reviews)
- [If participant sells products/services] How can customers leave feedback for you about your business online? What is the process for this helping shape your business?
Prompt: google reviews, product reviews, post, market analysis

Attacks on business or self

Purpose: Identifying the forms of attacks faced by business owners

Okay, I'm just going to shift the attention to when someone associated with your business intended to cause harm to your business; you can speak about either customers, ex-employees, or business partners. By "partner," we mean either a co-owner or significant collaborator that helps your business function.

By harm, you could think about any behavior or pattern of behavior that causes damage to your personal reputation, your branding, how your business functions, or your confidence to run your business as usual.

- Can you think back to a challenging time involving someone directly associated with your business?
Prompt: [dependent on account provided by participant]
- Have there been any occasions when you felt like someone associated with your business targeted you in a way that was intended to cause you harm? How did they do this? What was the impact on your business?
Prompt: persons involved, type of attack
- **[ONLY USE** If participant is struggling to think of an example] Can you think of a time where someone [impersonated you/smeared your reputation online/attempted a business takeover/maliciously reported you/coerced you financially/shared private information 'doxxed' you]*?

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Prompt: persons involved, attack vectors, steps to mitigate harm

- [Summarize the participant account from the previous question] When this happened, what kinds of steps did you take in response to this?

Prompt: take steps to mitigate harm, ask a friend/family member

- Did you send a report to the platform about this? How satisfied were you with their response?

Prompt: timeline, lack of communication

Suggestions for Business-Relevant Platforms

Purpose: Identifying what business owners would have wanted to help mitigate harm

Now that we've talked about the different ways you've faced harm with your business, I'd like to chat a little bit about what you think platforms could have done or should do in the future to help out scenarios like the ones you've described.

- [Answer dependent] Let's think back to [account provided by participant], can you think of any specific things the platforms you use could have done to help you as a business owner in dealing with the individual's actions in the moment?

Prompt: which platforms, why it'd be helpful, impact on interviewer

- [If participant is struggling with coming up with particular things] For instance, are there specific actions the platform could have provided that would have helped you prevent the individual from contacting you?

Prompt: which platforms, why it'd be helpful, impact on interviewer

- [Answer dependent] To expand on that, was there anything the platform could have done to better support you as you tried to recover from the challenging circumstance?

Prompt improving communication, financial help, regaining access, filing reports

Conclusions

This concludes the main portion of our interview, thank you so much for sharing your perspectives! Here, we would like to open the stage up for any questions or additional comments from your end, whether that be thoughts for the interview process, or any questions you might have for us.

In terms of next steps, we will use the notes from this interview in our analysis of your account which we will transform into a research paper. We are intending to use this as a tool to advocate for platforms to provide better protections for people in your position.

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If you'd like, we can send this final product to you to present how the analysis represented the important experiences you have spoken to us about.

Please do feel free to reach out to us if you have any additional questions.

Notes for researcher

*for more information about specific attacks ...

- *Impersonation*
 - Have you ever had a customer or close party attempt to impersonate you or your business?
 - How did that affect how your business or you operate?
 - What kinds of steps did you try to take to mitigate this harm? Did platforms offer any sort of reprieve in shutting down these impersonation attempts?
 - Examples include: impersonating on social media, impersonating on an online marketplace.
- *Reputation*
 - Have you ever had a customer or close party attempt to harm your reputation or your business' reputation?
 - How did that affect how your business or you operate?
 - What kinds of steps did you try to take to mitigate this harm?
 - Examples include: reputational harm through a series of targeted reviews or harmful comments on social media.
- *Business Takeover*
 - Have you ever had your business taken over by someone else in any way? Perhaps legally or through coercion by a business partner?
 - How did that affect your business and have you been able to mitigate the effects of that? What kinds of mechanisms were helpful in getting that fixed?
 - Examples include: Compromising a payment platform account, compromising the online marketplace account itself, gathering false evidence to legally takeover the business.
- *Inappropriate Reporting*
 - Has anyone ever unjustly reported your business in an effort to cause harm or disparage the reputation of your business?
 - What platform did this happen on?
 - What kinds of affordances did the platform provide in order to mitigate these false reports?
 - Examples include: Reporting or submitting a complaint to the Better Business Bureau, reporting your social media marketing posts, reporting business as fraudulent on online marketplace. Repeated online chargebacks on products or services sold.
- *Harassment*
 - Have you ever faced any form of real life or online harassment regarding your business that has affected you or the business?
 - If online, what platform(s) might this have happened on?
 - Were there any mechanisms in place to help you recover or avoid this harassment in the long term? For instance, any blocking mechanisms?
 - Examples include: Repeated private hateful or harmful messages on a social media or marketing platform, repeated phone calls and mail.
- *Coercion*
 - Have you had to face any form of coercion or force by another party while running your business? This may include being forced to provide a product, or other information about you or your business.
 - Examples include: Forcing a business owner to cosign on a business loan, coercing for business-related discounts or expenses, holding funding hostage due to prior relationships with the business owner.
- *Doxxing*
 - Have you ever had private information about you or your business publicised without consent by another party?
 - What kinds of ramifications did this have for your business?
 - Were you able to find means of support to get such information releases removed from platforms?

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- Examples include: Customers revealing personal addresses and phone numbers, private information regarding business' supply chain being revealed.